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FACTORS AND PRINCIPLES FOR DEVELOPING INFORMATION LITERACY IN DEAF AND HARD OF HEARING HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: This study aims to identify the factors and principles of the formation and development of information competence of deaf and hard of hearing high school students. During the work, the concept of «information competence» and its features in inclusive education were studied through theoretical and analytical analysis; at the empirical stage, students' ability to work with information was assessed using survey, observation and testing methods in a special educational institution. The main focus was on improving their information competence through the use of an adapted educational and methodological model (graphic, visual, interactive) and information technologies (digital platforms, mobile applications). The results of the study showed that the skills of students with hearing impairments to search, understand, process and independently use information significantly increased with the help of an integrated model and appropriate materials.

Key words: Deaf-hearing, hard of hearing, information literacy, inclusive education, adapted teaching-methodological model, information technologies, e-learning platform, multimodal education, learning skills, special education.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot kar va eshitish qobiliyati zaif o'rta maktab o'quvchilarining axborot kompetensiyasini shakllantirish va rivojlantirish omillari va tamoyillarini aniqlashga qaratilgan. Ish davomida «axborot kompetensiyasi» tushunchasi va uning inklyuziv ta'limdagi xususiyatlari nazariy va analitik tahlil orqali o'rganildi; empirik bosqichda maxsus ta'lim muassasasida o'quvchilarning axborot bilan ishlash qobiliyati so'rovnoma, kuzatish va test usullari yordamida baholandi. Asosiy e'tibor moslashtirilgan o'quv-metodik model (grafik, vizual, interaktiv) va axborot texnologiyalaridan (raqamli platformalar, mobil ilovalar) foydalanish orqali ularning axborot kompetensiyasini oshirishga qaratildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, eshitish qobiliyati zaif o'quvchilarning axborotni qidirish, tushunish, qayta ishlash va mustaqil ravishda foydalanish ko'nikmalari integratsiyalashgan model va tegishli materiallar yordamida sezilarli darajada oshdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kar eshitish qobiliyati zaif, eshitish qobiliyati zaif, axborot savodxonligi, inklyuziv ta'lim, moslashtirilgan o'qitish-metodik model, axborot texnologiyalari, elektron ta'lim platformasi, multimodal ta'lim, o'rganish ko'nikmalari, maxsus ta'lim.

Аннотация: Целью данного исследования является выявление факторов и принципов формирования и развития информационной компетентности глухих и слабослышащих старшеклассников. В ходе работы изучалось понятие «информационная компетентность» и её особенности в инклюзивном образовании посредством теоретико-аналитического анализа; на эмпирическом этапе оценивалась способность обучающихся работать с информацией с помощью методов анкетирования, наблюдения и тестирования в условиях специального образовательного учреждения. Основное внимание уделялось повышению их информационной компетентности посредством использования адаптированной учебно-методической модели (графической, визуальной, интерактивной) и информационных технологий (цифровых платформ, мобильных приложений). Результаты исследования показали, что навыки поиска, понимания, обработки и самостоятельного использования информации у обучающихся с нарушениями слуха существенно повысились при использовании интегрированной модели и соответствующих материалов.

Ключевые слова: глухие, слабослышащие, информационная грамотность, инклюзивное образование, адаптированная учебно-методическая модель, информационные технологии, платформа электронного обучения, мультимодальное образование, навыки обучения, специальное образование.

INTRODUCTION

In today's education system, the principles of inclusive education and equal opportunities should become not only the norm, but also a criterion of social justice. Expanding the opportunities for students with hearing impairments — deaf and hard of hearing — to receive information, acquire knowledge and use modern technologies is an urgent issue. Especially in higher grades — the skills of acquiring knowledge based on information resources, Internet sources, electronic platforms, visual and interactive materials are important. Therefore, the development of “information literacy” through the creation of adapted pedagogical models and educational conditions for them is an important step towards strengthening the principles of inclusion, equality and efficiency in education.

In the age of digital technologies, the education system is constantly developing and provides new opportunities based on the rapid spread of information technologies, innovative approaches and methodologies in education. This process is especially important for deaf and hard of hearing students. By developing their information competence, they are creating opportunities to expand their knowledge, actively participate in the educational process, and fully integrate into society.

Information competence, that is, the ability to effectively use information technologies, affects not only the rapid and accurate perception of information presented by teachers, but also the ability of students to think independently, solve problems, and apply the information they have learned in practice. The development of this competence in relation to deaf and hard-of-hearing students requires specific pedagogical approaches and methodological tools. In this article, we will try to explain the importance of this problem by considering the factors and effective principles that influence the development of students' information competence.

The development of information competence in senior school students is very important for their success in the modern information society. A number of factors and principles play an important role in this process.

Factors for the development of information competence:

Pedagogical factors:

- The level of teachers' use of information technologies.
- The use of interactive methods (projects, discussions, problem-based learning).
- Effective use of digital resources (online platforms, electronic textbooks) in education.

Technological factors:

- Availability of modern computers, the Internet and software in the school.
- The ability to use special programs for searching, analyzing and systematizing information (for example,

Google Scholar, Mendeley).

Socio-psychological factors:

- Formation of critical thinking and independent learning skills in students.
- Development of a culture of information exchange in collective work.

Personal factors:

- Students' personal interest in searching, evaluating and processing information.
- Their level of computer literacy and digital culture.

Organizational factors:

- The school library is equipped with modern resources.
- Conduct training on information security and ethical rules.

Axborot kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish tamoyillari:

Several studies have been conducted in the education system of Uzbekistan on the development of information literacy of deaf and hard of hearing students. In particular, there are a number of scientific works on creating opportunities for students in inclusive education and special education to use information technologies. These studies are aimed at improving students' skills in using information technologies and digital tools.

Research conducted by leading educators and psychologists of Uzbekistan has shown the problems of the opportunities and needs of deaf and hard of hearing students in the educational process. For example, the works of U.O.Turayev and Z.S.Muhammadjonov have highlighted the importance of educational methodologies in developing students' information literacy in the process of inclusive education. Their research has emphasized the need for specially adapted educational materials and methods for deaf and hard of hearing students.

Also, T.K. Tursunov and X.P. Rahimov in their works showed the introduction of information technologies into the educational process and their adaptation to the individual capabilities of students. Research also calls on teachers to use specific pedagogical approaches and didactic principles for students to be successful in education.

The factors for the development of students' information competence depend on a number of factors. Among them:

Pedagogical approaches. Teachers should use an individual approach to integrating information technologies into the educational process. Teachers should choose different methodologies in accordance with the characteristics, intellectual potential and auditory capabilities of students.

The use of information technologies in education. It is necessary to develop and use interactive platforms, audiovisual tools and special programs for deaf and hard of hearing students. These can be effective tools in developing students' information literacy.

Inclusive education system. It is important to introduce an inclusive approach in the educational process, that is, to take into account the needs of each student. Educational methodologies and materials adapted to deaf and hard of hearing students increase their interest in learning.

In addition, studies show that in developing students' information literacy, constant analysis and monitoring systems are needed to strengthen and promote dialogue and active participation with them. In order to further improve the opportunities for deaf and hard of hearing students to use information technologies, it is important to conduct teacher training courses, improve educational programs and provide them with new methodological tools.

CONCLUSION

The issue of developing information literacy of deaf and hard of hearing students should become an important part of the educational process in Uzbekistan. In order to ensure the effective use of information technologies by students, it is necessary to introduce special methodologies and innovative approaches within the educational system. This, in turn, will help to improve the knowledge and skills of students, ensure their integration into society, and improve the quality of education. The research and analysis presented in the article will provide guidelines for further research based on effective approaches and methodologies in developing information literacy of deaf and hard of hearing students.

A systematic approach is needed to develop information literacy of senior students, taking into account technological, pedagogical, and personal factors. Special attention should be paid to practical projects, critical analysis skills, and the effective use of digital resources in the educational process.

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